

PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING METHOD AND THE LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SCIENCE 9

JOBELLE O. ORIAS¹

ELISA N. CHUA, PhD²

14-S-MA-095@lspu.edu.ph¹

elisa.chua@lspu.edu.ph²

Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the learning outcomes of the students in Science 9 through the use of different problem-based learning method. Furthermore, this attempted to determine the student performance outcome as to their problem-based learning in terms of explanatory knowledge, descriptive knowledge, procedural knowledge, personal knowledge and to find out if there is a significant difference in the students problem-based learning outcomes when group according to the teaching method as to explanation problem, fact-finding problem, strategy problem, moral dilemma. Using an experimental design of research, it involved four (4) groups in grade 9 at San Antonio National High School with forty (40) students each during the academic year 2020-2021. A teacher-made module and performance task rubrics were used to measure the learning outcomes of the students when group according to the problem-based learning method which were validated by the panel of experts. Result revealed that there is a significant difference in the students' problem-based learning outcomes when group according to the teaching method as to explanation problem, fact-finding problem, strategy problem and moral dilemma. It also showed that students performance outcome as to their PBL in terms of explanatory knowledge, descriptive knowledge, procedural knowledge and personal knowledge fall under the category of proficient level.

Keywords: Problem-Based Learning, Learning Outcomes, PBL method, Science 9